

**PRINCIPAL’S LEADERSHIP APPROACHES AND TEACHERS’ EFFECTIVENESS
IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA**

BY

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Abstract

The study examined the relationship between principals’ leadership approaches and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. A sample of 540 teachers and principals was drawn from a population of 3600 using stratified random sampling across 216 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Instrument for sample selection were two sets of self- structured instruments titled ‘Principal Leadership Questionnaire (PLQ) and Teacher Effective Questionnaire (TEQ) in public secondary schools.’ The instruments were subjected to face validity by three experts. The reliability coefficient values of 0.80 and 0.79 were respectively obtained for both instruments using Cronbach’s Alpha. The instruments were distributed to the selected principals and teachers in the study’s areas of coverage. Data obtained were analysed with Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Statistics. Findings from the study revealed that, transformational, participative, and instructional leadership approaches significantly enhance teacher effectiveness. Significant relationships were found in all the three null hypotheses. The study concluded that, leadership approaches such as transformational, participative and instructional foster positive outcomes including enhanced teacher motivation, instructional quality and professional commitment. It was therefore recommended among others that, principals should focus on motivating, supporting and mentoring teachers; and also prioritize instructional supervision and curriculum implementation.

Keywords: Principal, Transformational Leadership, Participative Leadership, Instructional leadership, and Teacher Effectiveness

Introduction

Education is universally acknowledged as a cornerstone for national development, and the effectiveness of teachers remains a critical determinant of educational quality and student achievement. In the context of public secondary schools, particularly in developing regions like Bayelsa State, Nigeria, the role of school leadership especially that of principals has become increasingly central to driving instructional improvement and fostering teacher effectiveness. As the administrative and

instructional heads of schools, principals are expected to provide strategic direction, create enabling environments, and support teachers in delivering high-quality education (Bada et al., 2024).

Teacher effectiveness, broadly defined as the capability of teachers to facilitate meaningful learning and improve student outcomes, is influenced by a range of factors including pedagogical competence, classroom management, motivation, and professional development (König et al.,

2023; Taylor & Thion, 2023). However, research consistently shows that leadership practices within schools significantly shape these factors. Principals who adopt transformational, instructional, or participative leadership styles tend to inspire greater teacher commitment, innovation, and performance (Akomodì, 2025). Alternatively, authoritarian leadership can demoralize teachers, reduce instructional quality, and hinder student achievement.

In Bayelsa State, public secondary schools face a unique set of challenges, including underfunding, inadequate infrastructure, teacher shortages, and socio-political instability. These conditions demand leadership approaches that are not only adaptive and visionary but also responsive to the contextual realities of the state. Despite the critical role of principals in charting these challenges, there is a scarcity of empirical research investigating how their leadership approaches affect extensively teacher effectiveness in this specific setting. Most existing studies have focused on other states of Nigeria, leaving a significant knowledge gap regarding the dynamics at play in Bayelsa's educational landscape (Nwachukwu & Nwosa, 2025). This study, therefore, seeks to examine the relationship between principals' leadership approaches and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. By exploring how different leadership approaches such as transformational, instructional, and participative affect teacher effectiveness.

Statement of the Problem

The quality of education in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State continues to face serious challenges, including declining student performance, low teacher morale, and inconsistent instructional delivery. At the centre of these challenges lies the critical role of school leadership particularly that of secondary principals whose leadership approaches can either improve or hinder teacher effectiveness. In a state like Bayelsa, which is marked by infrastructural deficits, limited resources, and socio-economic instability, the leadership approach adopted by school principals becomes a determining factor in shaping the professional behaviour, motivation, and instructional quality of teachers.

Despite national and state-level efforts to improve educational outcomes, empirical evidence suggests that many public secondary schools in Bayelsa still struggle to meet expected standards of teaching and learning (Nwachukwu & Nwosa, 2025). Teachers often operate in challenging environments with minimal support, and the extent to which principals provide instructional guidance, foster collaboration, and create enabling conditions for effective teaching remains unclear. While studies have established that leadership practices such as transformational and instructional leadership positively influence teacher effectiveness in other Nigerian states (Bada et al., 2024), there is a dearth of localized research examining how these dynamics unfold within the unique socio-cultural and economic context of Bayelsa State.

This gap in knowledge presents a critical problem: without a nuanced understanding of how principals' leadership approaches affect teacher effectiveness in Bayelsa's public secondary schools, educational stakeholders may continue to implement generic policies that fail to address the root causes of underperformance. Therefore, this study investigated the relationship between principals' leadership approaches and teachers' effectiveness, with the aim of generating context-specific insights that can inform leadership development, teacher support strategies, and policy reforms in the state's education sector.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between principals' leadership approaches and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between principals' transformational leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
2. Determine the relationship between principals' participative leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa state.
3. Examine the relationship between principals' instructional leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa state.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the relationship between principals' transformational leadership approach and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' participative leadership approach and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
3. What is the relationship between principals' instructional leadership approach and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between principals' transformational leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between principals' participative leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between principals' instructional leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Review Of Related Literature

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on House's Path-Goal Theory (1971), which explains how

leaders enhance subordinates' performance by clarifying goals, removing obstacles, and providing appropriate motivation and support. The theory posits that leadership effectiveness depends on the alignment between leadership behaviours, followers' needs, and the work environment. Within the context of public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, principals' transformational, instructional, and participative leadership approaches represent leadership behaviours that influence teachers' effectiveness. Transformational leadership motivates and inspires teachers by articulating a shared vision and fostering professional growth, thereby strengthening teachers' commitment and confidence to achieve instructional goals. Instructional leadership aligns with the directive dimension of Path–Goal Theory by clarifying instructional expectations, supervising teaching activities, and providing guidance on curriculum implementation, which reduces role ambiguity and enhances classroom effectiveness. Participative leadership reflects the participative leadership behaviour in Path–Goal Theory, as it involves teachers in decision-making processes, increases their sense of ownership, and promotes collaboration and innovation in teaching. Consistent with Path–Goal Theory, the study assumes that when principals adopt leadership behaviours that match teachers' needs and school conditions, teachers are more likely to demonstrate higher levels of instructional effectiveness, classroom management, and professional commitment. Thus, Path–Goal Theory provides a relevant theoretical foundation for explaining how principals'

leadership approaches contribute to teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Conceptual Clarification

Principal's leadership approach refers to the actions, behaviours, and strategies employed by school principals to influence teaching, learning and school culture toward achieving educational goals. It encompasses instructional guidance, organizational management, and the ability to foster a positive school climate. Corrigan and Merry (2022) described principal leadership as the ability of school leaders to adapt their behaviours and strategies to meet the evolving demands of 21st-century education, innovation, and responsiveness to change. Across these definitions, several core elements emerge and of which some are transformational leadership; instructional leadership, and participative leadership approaches.

Principal's Transformational Leadership Approach

Principal transformational leadership is a leadership practice that inspires, and motivates teachers through vision, encouragement, and personal support. It emphasizes change, development, and performance through charisma. Agazu et al. (2025) described transformational leadership as a leadership approach that is characterized by the capacity of a leader to inspire, and motivate followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes by transforming their beliefs, values, and objectives of that of the organization. Principal transformational leadership provides

financial resources for teachers' professional development and implement decisions jointly taken with teachers thereby giving them a sense of belonging (Towler, 2019).

Principal's Participative Leadership Approach

Participative or democratic leadership approach is a leadership style that allows every team member to be involved and work together with others in the decision-making process. The participative leader consults his team members concerning work related matters, solicit their opinions and in most cases attempt to adopt team members' idea in decision-making process (Northouse, 2018). Participative leadership approach involves shared decision making and inclusivity. It improves teacher effectiveness, student outcomes and school climate (Ginggar, 2025; Uwamahoro, 2024). In a participative school leadership approach, the principal emphasizes open communication, collaboration, and respect for diverse opinions. He guides his teachers rather than dictate. He encourages creativity and innovation. Karoli and Upadhayaya, (2024) observe that, participative leadership in school encourages curriculum innovation and professional growth. It leads to higher teacher job satisfaction, and enhances student academic outcome through collaborative culture (Mohamud & Muiru, 2024).

Principal's Instructional Leadership Approach

Instructional leadership is a leadership approach that prioritize the enhancement of

teaching and learning by focusing on curriculum development, teacher support, and student academic achievement (Akomodi, 2025). Instructional principals create conditions for teacher effectiveness, and student achievement (Liu et al., 2022). Principal instructional leadership set clear academic expectations and shared vision, construct feedback and coaching, and make regular classroom observation. Akomodi (2025) observed that effective leadership is linked to improved teacher morale, student engagement, and overall school performance and that instructional leadership can create positive educational atmosphere that enhances classroom achievement and provide support, and resources for teacher's professional development. In its global education monitoring report.

Teacher Effectiveness

Teacher effectiveness refers to the extent to which a teacher successfully promotes student learning, engagement and achievement through high quality instruction, classroom management and professional competence. Taylor and Thion (2023) describe teacher effectiveness as the degree to which teachers' instructional practices and professional behaviours contribute to measurable improvement in students learning engagement. An effective teacher has the ability to inspire and significantly affect the lives of his students. Effective teachers demonstrate strong content and pedagogical knowledge; positively impact student academic outcome; maintain a positive and inclusive classroom environment; use varied

instructional strategies and engage in continuous professional learning. Several internal and external factors shape teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools and some of these factors are: Leadership support; professional development; school environment; teacher motivation and job satisfaction (Bada et al., 2024; Nwachukwu & Nwosa 2025)

Methods

The study adopted correlational research design. Salkind (2017) defined correlational research as a research that, investigates the relationship between two or more variables. Correlational design is ideal for this study because, it aligns with the aim of the study which is examining the relationship between principals’ leadership approaches and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Three research questions guided the study and corresponding null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A sample of 540 teachers and principals was drawn from a population of 3600 teachers in all the public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The source of information on population of teachers was obtained from Bayelsa state secondary school board. The stratified random sampling technique was

employed to select 15% of the total population of principals and teachers as respondents while simple random sampling technique was used to select 27 out of 216 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Instrument for sample selection were two sets of self- developed instruments titled ‘Principal Leadership Questionnaire (PLQ) and Teacher Effective Questionnaire (TEQ). A total of 540 copies of the instruments were administered to selected respondents. However, only 472 copies representing 87% of the total number of questionnaires administered were retrieved on the spot by the researcher and his research assistants. The instruments were subjected to face and content validity by three experts from the department of Foundations, Arts and Social Sciences, Federal University Otueke. Reliability was confirmed with Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of 0.78 and 0.79 respectively. Data obtained from the research questions and the null hypotheses were analysed with Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). The criterion Mean of 2.50 was adopted as benchmark to accept and reject an item based on the 4-point Likert’s scale. Any value that is equal-to or above the criterion mean was considered accepted and any below was considered rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between principals’ transformational leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) on the relationship between principals’ transformational leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Variables	No of Respondents	R-Calculated	Remark
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Transformational Leadership Approach	0.84	Very High Positive Relationship
Teacher Effectiveness	472	

The result from table 1 revealed Pearson’s correlation co-efficient (r) value of 0.84 indicating a very high and positive relationship between principals’ transformational leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between principals’ participative leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) on the relationship between principals’ participative leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Variables	No of Respondent	R	Remark
Participative Leadership Approach		0.79	
Teacher Effectiveness	472		High Positive Relationship

The result from table 2 revealed Pearson’s correlation co-efficient (r) value of 0.79 indicating a high and positive relationship between principals’ participative leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between principals’ instructional leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) on the relationship between principals’ instructional leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Variables	No of Respondents	R-calculated	Remark
Instructional Leadership Approach		0.79	
Teacher Effectiveness	472		High Positive Relationship

The result from table 3 revealed Pearson’s correlation co-efficient (r) value of 0.79 indicating a high and positive relationship between principals’ instructional leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

H01: There is no significant relationship between principals’ transformational leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between principals’ transformational leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness

Variables	No. of Respondents	R-calculated	p-value	Decision
Transformational Leadership	472	0.84	Rejected 0.00	
Teachers’ Effectiveness				

Result from table 4 reveals a correlation coefficient value of 0.81 with a p- value of 0.00 at 0.05 level of significance. This simply implies that, since the p-value = 0.00 < 0.05 there is a significant

relationship between principals’ transformational leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, therefore the null hypothesis 1 was rejected. In addition, the Pearson’s correlation coefficient $r = 0.84$ indicates a very high positive relationship between principals’ transformational leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between principals’ participative leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between principals’ participative leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness

Variables	No. of Respondents	R-Calculated	p-value	Remark
Participative Leadership		0.79	0.00	Rejected
Teacher Effectiveness				

Result from table5. reveals a correlation coefficient value of 0.79 with a p- value of 0.00 at 0.05 level of significance. This simply implies that, since the $p\text{-value} = 0.00 < 0.05$ there is a significant relationship between principals’ participative leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, therefore

the null hypothesis 1 was rejected. In addition, the Pearson’s correlation coefficient r was 0.84 indicating a high positive relationship between principals’ participative leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between principals’ instructional leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between principals’ instructional leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness

Variables	No of Respondents	R-calculated	p-value	Remark
Instructional Leadership			Rejected	
Teacher Effectiveness		0.79	0.00	

Result from table 6 reveals a correlation coefficient value of 0.81 with a p- value of 0.00 at 0.05 level of significance. This simply implies that, since the $p\text{-value} = 0.00 < 0.05$, there is a significant relationship between principals’ instructional leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, therefore

the null hypothesis 3 was rejected. In addition, the Pearson’s correlation coefficient r was 0.79 indicating a high positive relationship between principals’ instructional leadership approach and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Discussion

Transformational Leadership Approach

Findings from research question one and hypothesis one revealed that the Pearson's correlation co-efficient (r) value was 0.84 and the p-value = $0.00 < 0.05$ indicating a very high, positive, and significant relationship between principals' transformational leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This simply implies that transformational leadership approach motivates and enhances teacher effectiveness. This finding is consistent with the study of Towler (2019) who elucidated that, principal transformational leaders help teachers to be autonomous, provides financial resources for their' professional development, and implement decisions jointly taken with them and this gives the teachers a sense of belonging.

Participative Leadership

Findings from research question 2 and hypothesis 2 revealed that the Pearson's correlation co-efficient (r) value was 0.79 and the p-value = $0.00 < 0.05$ indicating a high, positive, and significant relationship between principals' participative leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This simply implies that participative leadership approach encourages and enhances teacher effectiveness. This finding gained the support of Karoli and Upadhayaya, (2024) who hinted that, participative leadership in school encourages curriculum innovation and professional growth. Participative leadership approach involves shared

decision making and inclusivity. It improves teacher effectiveness, student outcomes and school climate (Ginggar, 2025; Uwanahoro, 2024).

Instructional Leadership Approach

Findings from research question 3 and hypothesis 3 indicated that the Pearson's correlation co-efficient (r) value was 0.79 and the p-value = $0.00 < 0.05$ indicating a high, positive, and significant relationship between principals' instructional leadership approach and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. In other words, instructional leadership approach encourages and enhances teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This finding is in line with the study of Liu et al. (2022) who asserted that instructional leadership creates conditions for teacher effectiveness, and student achievement. Similarly, Akomodi (2025) observed that instructional leadership can create positive educational atmosphere that enhances classroom achievement and provide support, and resources for teacher's professional development.

Conclusion

The study revealed that principals' leadership approaches significantly influence teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Leadership approaches such as transformational, participative and instructional were found to enhance teachers' motivation and professional development, classroom management, instructional delivery and overall

commitment to students' academic achievement.

Recommendations

1. Promote transformational, participative and instructional leadership training: Educational authorities should organize regular workshops to train principals on focusing on teacher growth and development, involving teachers in decision-making processes, and monitor and support teacher effectiveness.
2. Principals should focus on motivating, supporting and mentoring teachers; and also prioritize instructional supervision and curriculum implementation

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